

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16920776

Attitude Of Students Towards Homosexuality Practices In Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the attitude of students towards homosexuality practices in secondary schools in Rivers State. Five research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. The research design used in this study was survey research. The population of this study consisted of all secondary school students in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt city Local Government Areas of Rivers state totaling thirty-eight thousand and five Hundred and eighteen (38,518). In determining the sample size for the study, simple random sampling technique was adopted; thus, the sample size for the study was 400 students. A researcher-made instrument titled “Attitude of Students Towards Homosexuality Scale (ASTHS) was used for obtaining information from the respondents, in which the supervisor and other experts in Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling department were consulted to review the instrument and its items. The reliability of 0.86 was obtained which showed that the instrument was reliable. The data analysis was carried out using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions stated in chapter one of this study, while independent t-test was adopted for the testing of the formulated null hypotheses at 0.05 (i.e. 5%) level of probability. The findings of the study showed that the attitude of students towards homosexual practices is not subjected to gender, socio-economic status, class level, religious denomination, and home status. Again, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of the students’ responses on their attitude towards homosexual practices based on gender, socio-economic status, class level, religious denomination and home status.

Keywords: Attitude, homosexuality, practices, students

INTRODUCTION

In recent time, one of the topical issues in the entire world is homosexuality. In most parts of the world including Africa, the notion of homosexuality has been very hostile among those who practice it (Sollar & Somda, 2011). In addition, homosexuality is perceived as sex interest predominantly in persons of the same sex (Canto, 2012). In the case of Nigerian society, homosexuality is regarded as one of the evils of our time. However, a closer look shows that these practices have been with us in many cultures bearing various names, and obviously not elevated to the present-day status it enjoys.

The foregoing is confirmed by Kendell (1995), who reported about forms of intimate relations practiced in South Africa; that even though indigenous African communities do not have names for same sex relationship does not mean that such relationships were alien (Kendell, 1995). Any meaningful attempt to discuss sexuality today requires us to also explain the concept of gender identity. Kinanee & Gilbert (2015), espoused that gender identity is a person’s sense of themselves as either male or female irrespective of the person’s biological sex. The way and manner in which the person expresses his or her gender is called gender expression.

In terms of sexual orientation, homosexuality is a process in which people are attracted to persons of the same sex, and those who are in these activities are termed homosexuals (gay or lesbian). Meanwhile, individuals that are attracted to opposite sex are regarded as being “straight”. Generally, a gay is a male homosexual while a lesbian is referred to as a female homosexual. A person who does not experience any sexual attraction is called asexual. A transgender is one though born as male or female has the gender identity of the opposite sex. It has also been revealed that a transgender person

could change his or her sex anatomy either in part or whole which could be affected through hormonal treatment or surgery. Living in a heterosexist society inevitably poses a challenge to people with non-heterosexual orientation. Many lesbians, gay and bisexual people face social stigma, heterosexism, violence and discrimination (Herek, 1991a, 2009; Mays & Cochran, 2001; Meryer, 2003).

The phenomenon heterosexism is an ideological system that denies, denigrates and stigmatizes any non-heterosexual form of behaviour, identity, relationship, or community (Herek, 1995). It occurs at all levels from the cultural to the individual. At the cultural level, gays and lesbians are placed squarely outside of the model life course and lifestyle. Cultural heterosexism involves the social phenomenon that creates and maintains anti-homosexual sentiment (Herek, 1990). At the cultural level, heterosexism is manifest by phenomena such as the denial of marriage rights to gays and lesbians. These kinds of biases filter through social institutions and face-to-face interactions all the way down to each person's thoughts, feelings, and behaviours. Heterosexism at the individual level and psychological heterosexism involves a specific person's homo-negative belief and value system, as well as their cognitive affective and behavioural reactions to gays and lesbians.

Research regarding the attitude towards gay men and lesbians often used the term "homophobia" to characterize a negative attitude schema towards homosexual (Herek, 2004). However, recently the term has come under criticism due to its implication that anti-gay prejudice is based on fear (Herek, 2004). As a result, Herek (2004) introduced the term "sexual prejudice" to more accurately represent negative attitude towards sexually stigmatized groups such as gay men, lesbians and transgender individuals. Sexual prejudice is operationally seen as negative attitude base on sexual orientation. Attitude towards gay men and lesbians are multidimensional and to fully understand anti-gay prejudice, these different aspects of people's attitudes and perceptions must be considered. This stems from the fact that attitude towards homosexuality can serve different functions for different people (Herek, 1986). The most detrimental effects of homophobia is the potential negative impact on LGB mental health. In fact, it is believed that living in a homophobic society creates unique stressors for LGBT individuals. Hence, any belief system that supports negative myths and stereotypes about homosexual people, or any of the varieties of negative attitude that arises from fear or dislike of homosexuality is homophobia. It is an irrational fear of homosexuals and homosexuality. Homophobes react to homosexuals as enemies to be feared, hated, and actively repressed (Mihalk, 1991).

Indigenous Africans, including those in South Africa, regard being gay/lesbian or transsexual as un-African; in fact, a former Nigerian Justice Minister Bayo Ojo described homosexuality "as unnatural and un-African". Kinanee & Ezekiel-Hart (2012), one described the hostile attitude towards these people as easily traced to religious and traditional beliefs. In an anonymous survey on LGBT people (2016) published by Global Attitude Survey on societal attitude towards homosexuality using 54 countries across the continents, Nigeria ranked first among the countries which agree that LGBT should be a crime, with 59% in the affirmative. Closely following Nigeria is Ghana 54%, Saudi Arabia 49%, Jordan 47% UAE 45% and Egypt 44%. On the other hand, the countries which view that LGBT should not be a crime ranked as follows: Netherland 76%, Portugal 75%, Italy 74%, Ireland 73%, Spain, and Croatia 72% with South Africa 61% as the highest in Africa. The above finding corroborates the claim of the Nigerian Government in enacting the Anti-Gay Law (2014) which criminalized homosexual relationships and activities. It also shows that apart from South Africa, the countries that are supportive to the sensibilities of LGBT are mainly in Europe and America. Culture, tradition, and religion appear to impose great influence on the attitude of people towards sexual minorities (Femi, 2011), and Kinanee & Ezekiel-Hart (2012) reported that Africa (especially Western and Central Africa) culture and tradition forbid same-sex relationship and consider it as evil, abominable, immoral, animalistic and unhealthy and posit that religious and traditional beliefs are responsible for such seemingly hostile attitudes.

The word homosexuality is used in this work to capture the practices of lesbians, gay men, bisexuals, and transgender (LGBT); and it has also become a major issue to public discourse. It is a delicate matter because on the one hand it is a personal affair, yet it has societal dimension. It is an area that has not enjoyed consensus of opinion as we find in the divergent positions taken by various countries, legislatures, courts, religion, organizations, professionals and the society at large. It has been found that even among groups that ordinary share same values like same religion, there is still divergence of views. In addition, the lack of consensus of opinion among professionals has been a challenge over

the years. Homosexuals do need medical as well as counselling attention which should be offered professionally. The attitude of the professional care givers is therefore central and affect the quality of service given. This is corroborated by the survey carried out by the California Medical Society (Smith & Matthew, 2007). Some work has been done on the religious and moral perspectives of homosexuality (Cochran, 2004; Feldblum, 2010; Nkosi & Masson, 2017, Onuche, 2014), but not much has been documented in the area on the attitude of students towards homosexuality practices and none has been domesticated in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The contextual problem of this study is that gay men, lesbians, and indeed all those who are currently classified as homosexuals constitute a group with peculiar sexual orientation. In addition, the widespread of the LGBT community has awakened the social perspectives of the society towards them. Nowadays there have also been a lot of changes towards the LGBT community on how they interact, and build their self in the society in a manner that fits them.

Young people are prone to change and could be better promoters of anti-stigma programme. This will have the added benefit of helping in spreading non homophobic attitude towards homosexuals. In an African context, the pressure to marry and have children with the strong social disapproval of homosexuality may partly explain the high rate of bisexuality. Most Christian denominations do not spare those who practice homosexuality. For instance, the general overseers of some Pentecostal denominations understand the question of homosexuality largely as in their words, as being “a presenting symptom, or presenting issue or presenting problem” and they also see it as an underlying disease. This explains why homosexuality is wrong within the Christian fold. This is because some Christians who are advocating for the blessing of same sex unions are effectively changing the gospel, quoting Saint Paul who included gay sex on a list of sins from which Christians need to repent.

Furthermore, the cultural community may be hostile to the gay men and lesbians, the church may deny them the right to marry, but the call for the world to live together in a global village has exposed the people (students’ alike) to different reactions to homosexual activities through the internet and digital satellite televisions. It is for this reason that for the young men who have sex with men, the internet may be a space to gain exposure to a number of sexuality related topics and experiences that may not be readily available to them. In the absence of more traditional sources of information about sexuality and the mechanics of sex such as schools, friends and family members’ pornography is available through the internet to provide the first glimpse of gay sexuality and locate other gay men. Those (either by choice or biologically) who wish to locate other homosexuals may do so through the internet.

As students are often in the later teenage stage of the life cycle (11–17 years), challenges with identity and intimacy are developmentally fitting. Furthermore, tensions between religious beliefs and sexual orientation could potentially impact on their studies and their ability to fulfill their academic potential, as well as their sense of wellbeing. It is on this backdrop that this study sought to understand the views and opinions in other words, the attitude of students towards homosexuality practices in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the attitude of students towards homosexuality practices in secondary schools in Rivers State. The study intends to also specifically determine:

1. The mean rating of students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on gender in Rivers State;
2. The mean rating of students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on socio-economic status of parents in Rivers State;
3. The mean rating of students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on class-level in Rivers State;
4. The mean rating of students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on religious persuasion in Rivers State;
5. The mean rating of students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on home status in Obio/Akpor LGA; and
6. The mean rating of students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on location in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following questions are to guide the study

1. What is the mean rating of students in secondary schools on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on gender in Rivers State?
2. What is the mean rating of students in secondary schools on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on socio-economic status of parents in Rivers State?
3. What is the mean rating of students in secondary schools on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on class-level in Rivers State?
4. What is the mean rating of students in secondary schools on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on religious persuasion in Rivers State?
5. What is the mean rating of students in secondary schools on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on home status in Rivers State?
6. What is the mean rating of students in secondary schools on their attitude towards homosexuality practices based on location in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

This study is guided by the following null hypotheses:

- Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female secondary school students in Rivers State on their attitude towards homosexuality practices.
- Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students from low and high socio-economic parental status in Rivers State on their attitude towards homosexuality practices.
- Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of junior and senior secondary school students in Rivers State on their attitude towards homosexuality practices.
- Ho₄: There is no significance difference between the mean rating of Pentecostal and non-Pentecostal secondary school students in Rivers State on their towards homosexuality practices.
- Ho₅: There is no significance difference between the mean rating of secondary school students from broken and non-broken homes in Rivers State on their attitude towards homosexuality practices.
- Ho₆: There is no significance difference between the mean rating of secondary school students from urban and rural areas in Rivers State on their attitude towards homosexuality practices.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on attribution theory which was first proposed by Heider in 1944, 1958 and later furthered by Weiner in 1979, 1985. The theory stated that individuals work to predict and control their environment by attributing others' behaviours as the result of internal or external factors. It also holds that people are motivated to assign causes to their actions and behaviours (Moskowitz, 2005). In social psychology, attribution is the process by which individuals explain the causes of behaviour and events (Kassin & Markus, 2010).

Empirical review

Lim, V.K.G. (2002), carried out a descriptive survey study on gender differences and attitudes towards homosexuality total population of 413 respondents in the survey (men=141; women=272). However, the sample respondents comprised 365 students and data were collected through the use of questionnaires. Results generally showed that both male and female have negative attitudes towards homosexuals. Their findings also revealed that, generally, women reported that they were more comfortable in working closely with male homosexuals while reverse was the case for men.

Dugmore and Cocker, (2008) reported that society is holistically becoming increasingly more accepting of the homosexual lifestyle, as compared to the late nineties. This is seen by the continuous passing of laws, acts and legal procedures in relation to the rights of homosexual persons. Furthermore, Dugmore and Cocker, (2008) believe that it is ethically and morally anticipated that social workers adhere to the lawful standards passed in the favor of a typical sexuality types. Social workers have a professional obligation to consider different family types, including LGBT individuals as a parental subsystem. Similar to Dugmore and Cocker (2008), Hicks (2008) believes that homosexuality is not a socioeconomic problem hence both children of high and low socioeconomic status are seen practicing homosexuality. Hicks (2008) considers that people contributing to the social

work profession need to deter from the idea of uncovering what it means to be a homosexual in a heterosexual world; rather social workers need to coexist with different sexuality types as humans contributing to society and to the betterment of fostered lives.

Odeigah, Rasaki, Ajibola, Hafsat, Sule, and Musah (2019), High risk sexual behaviour among adolescent senior secondary school students in Nigeria. The study gauged the level of knowledge and perceptions of high risk sexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Ilorin, Nigeria with a view to improving their understanding of the current trends in HRSP. This was a quantitative, cross-sectional, descriptive study of adolescent secondary school students in Ilorin East Local Government Area. Multi – stage sampling method involving 3 stages was used. A semi-structured interviewer administered questionnaire was used to obtain data. Informed consent of respondents was obtained. The data was analyzed using SPSS windows software package version 17. Their results showed that majority, 305 (69.5%) of the students were between 16 – 20 years. The major source of information was from movies, 42.5%, and the internet, 24.7%. Twenty-three percent (23.1%) had poor knowledge of HRSP. Thirty-eight percent (38.1%) did not consider indiscriminate sexual intercourse as HRSP while 27.9% still believed that unprotected sexual practice is safe. Thirty-four percent (34.2%) did not know that sex with multiple partners is a HRSP while 34.4% did not know that oral –genital sex is unsafe. Over thirty-two (32.9%) perceived that engaging in sex made them mature among peers. Twenty-four (24.7%) did not perceive any danger in keeping multiple sexual partners while 15.3% would still engage in unprotected sex. The students had relatively poor knowledge and perceptions of HRSP. Quite a number did not consider indiscriminate sexual intercourse as HRSP. An appreciable number did not perceive any danger in keeping multiple sexual partners or being engaged in unprotected sex. Counselling on the dangers of HRSP should be a component of the school health services so as to curb the complications of HRSP in our secondary schools.

Winnie, Elizabeth & McCoy (2016), in their study on grappling with the issue of homosexuality: perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs among high school students in Kenya. The purpose of this study was to examine high school students' perceptions of homosexuality in Kenya. The participants included 1,250 high school students who completed a questionnaire on perceptions of homosexuality. The results showed that 41% claimed homosexuality is practiced in schools and 61% believed homosexuality is practiced mostly in single-sex boarding schools. Consistently, 52% believed sexual starvation to be the main cause of homosexuality. Also, 95% believed homosexuality is abnormal, 60% believed students who engage in homosexuality will not change to heterosexuality after school, 64% believed prayers can stop homosexuality, and 86% believed counseling can change students' sexual orientation. The consequences for homosexuality included punishment (66%), suspension from school (61%), and expulsion from school (49%). Significant gender and grade differences were found. The implications of the study findings are discussed.

Public opinion research has repeatedly revealed a substantial association between religiousness and negative attitudes towards lesbians and gays (Olson et al., 2006; Stulhofer and Rimac, 2009; Whitley, 2009). Interestingly, such a relationship has been empirically demonstrated for several religious denominations. Finlay and Walther (2003), for example, analyzed negative attitudes towards homosexuals based on religious affiliation in the United State and found that members of Conservative Protestant denominations held the most negative attitudes towards homosexuals, followed by moderate Protestants and Catholics (Maher, 2013; Schwartz, 2012; Whitley, 2009).

The home which is the student's first place of settlement plays a vital role in the socialization process. Agbedanu (2012), posits that whatever behaviour put up by members of the family is what the student copies. For example, in a family where there is love, unity and peace, the student also grows up with these characteristics. Thus, the family background should be an environment in which students have the opportunity to succeed and be happy. Giddens & Sutton (2012) define family of the home 'a group of persons directly linked by kin connections, the adult members of which assume responsibility for caring for students' and 'kin' are those linked by marriage or blood relationships. The definition of Giddens and Sutton is of particular importance to this study because it talks of adult taking care of the student. This care may not be fully available for students in broken homes.

METHODOLOGY

The design used in this study is survey research. Survey research allowed structured questionnaire to be used for data collection from the respondents and also assisted the study to investigate the result of secondary school students' attitudes towards homosexuality practices accruing from gender differences, socio-economic status of parents, class level differences, religious denomination perceptions, as well as home status respectively. The population of this study consists of all secondary school students in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Information obtained from the supervising ministry indicate a total of seventy-four (74) secondary schools from the selected Local Government Areas with secondary students population put at thirty-eight Thousand five Hundred and eighteen (38,518) (Source: Post Primary School Management Board, 2018).

In determining the sample size for this study, simple random sampling technique was adopted. The sample size for the study is 400 students. The choice of sample size was adopted as stated by Omoniwa (2009), who recommended a sample size of Three hundred and Thirty-Five (335) and above, for a population of over Two Thousand and Six Hundred (2,600). A researcher-made instrument titled "Attitude of Students towards Homosexuality Scale (ASTHS) was used for obtaining information from the respondents. The instrument was designed alongside background knowledge acquired from sources of literature reviewed. Basically, the instrument was divided into two sections namely sections A and B. Section A seeks to gather respondents' information (bio-data); while section B elicited information based on research objectives. In order to gather the needed information for the study, the statements / items in the instrument were designed alongside four (4) point rating scales modified by Likert. The scales are as follows: Strongly Agreed (SA), 4 points, Agreed (A) – 3 points, Disagreed (D) – 2 points, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) – 1 point.

The instrument used in this study was developed by the researcher for the purpose of this study. Supervisors and other experts in the researchers' department were consulted to review the instrument and its items. The purpose was to ascertain face and content validity as is the case with research instruments. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a trial testing was done using 40 students which were not part of the sample. The purpose was to determine the internal consistency of the instrument in measuring what it was designed to measure. Therefore, the questionnaire was administered to students twice, the first week and two weeks after. The scores from the two measurements were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis. The reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained, which showed that the instrument was reliable for the study.

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from his department, which he took to the Inspectorate division of the Ministry of Education. This was to seek their approval and permission to allow him visit the schools. Teachers in the visited schools helped in the administration of the instrument because of the scope and time-frame of the study. A total number of 400 copies of the instrument was administered. In order to expect at least 95% return rate, this was executed in two (2) weeks duration. The data analysis was carried out using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions stated in chapter one of this study, while independent *t-test* was adopted for the testing of the formulated null hypotheses.

RESULTS**Answer to Research Questions**

Research Question One: *What are the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on gender?*

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviations on the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on gender

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std	Remark
1.	Boys need to know something about homosexuality	203	119	53	25	3.25	0.91	Agreed
2.	It is girls that need to know something about homosexuality	123	178	76	23	3.00	0.85	Agreed
3.	Homosexuality is a thing for the boys	135	160	77	28	3.01	0.90	Agreed
4.	It is a thing for the girls	42	133	171	54	2.41	0.85	Disagreed
5.	Homosexuality is most predominant among boys	30	149	156	65	2.36	0.84	Disagreed
6.	It is most predominant among girls.	25	126	187	62	2.29	0.80	Disagreed
7.	Homosexuality is for boys only.	71	140	34	155	2.32	1.16	Disagreed
8.	Lesbianism is for girls only	153	163	59	25	3.11	0.88	Agreed
9.	Homosexuality should be practiced among boys	47	85	111	157	2.06	1.04	Disagreed
10.	Lesbianism should be practiced among girls.	53	63	123	161	2.02	1.05	Disagreed
Grand Mean						2.58	0.93	Agreed

Table 4.1 shows the attitude of students towards homosexuality practices based on gender. The table shows clearly that the boys need to know something about homosexuality (Mean=3.25, SD=0.91), as well as the girls (Mean=3.00, SD=0.85), homosexuality is a thing for the boys (Mean=3.01, SD=0.90), lesbianism is for girls only (Mean=3.11, SD=0.88), however, it was disagreed that homosexuality is a thing for the girls (Mean=2.41, SD=0.85), homosexuality is most predominant among boys (Mean=2.36, SD=0.84), mostly predominant among girls (Mean=2.29, SD=0.80), for boys only (Mean=2.32, SD=1.16), should be practiced among boys (Mean=2.06, SD=1.04) and that lesbianism should be practiced among girls (Mean=2.02, SD=1.05)

Research Question Two: *What are the attitude towards homosexuality practices based on socio-economic status of parents?*

Table 4.2: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviations on the Attitude towards homosexuality practices based on socio-economic status of parents

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std	Remark
11	Lack of social amenities at home makes a student to indulge in sex-related behaviours.	42	48	225	85	2.12	0.86	Disagreed
12	Too much internet gadgets at students disposal can lead to homosexuality.	125	176	67	32	2.99	0.90	Agreed
13	Lack of freedom can lead to homosexuality	135	131	94	40	2.90	0.98	Agreed
14	Excessive freedom can lead to homosexuality	140	152	55	53	2.95	1.01	Agreed
15.	Maintaining social status can lead to homosexuality	35	59	162	144	1.96	0.93	Disagreed

16.	Too much money at students' disposal can lead to homosexuality	62	30	181	127	2.07	1.01	Disagreed
17.	Lack of money can lead to homosexuality	163	128	64	45	3.02	1.01	Agreed
18.	Acting on parents' instruction can lead to homosexuality	37	31	154	178	1.82	0.93	Disagreed
19.	Acting on fellow rich friends instruction can lead to homosexuality.	78	165	88	69	2.63	0.99	Agreed
10	Wealth (rich or poor) cannot lead to homosexuality.	98	87	120	95	2.47	1.10	Disagreed
Grand Mean						2.49	0.97	Disagreed

Table 4.2 showed the attitude of students towards homosexuality practices based on socio-economic status. The table showed clearly that too much internet gadgets at students' disposal (Mean=.99, SD=0.90), lack of freedom (Mean=2.90, SD=0.98), lack of money (Mean=3.02, SD=1.01) and acting on fellow rich friends' instruction (Mean=2.63, SD=0.99) can all lead to homosexuality. On the other hand, the students disagreed that lack of social amenities at home makes a student to indulge in sex-related behaviours (Mean=2.12, SD=0.86), maintaining social status (Mean=1.96, SD=0.93), too much money at students' disposal (Mean=2.07, SD=1.01), wealth (rich or poor), (Mean=2.47, SD=1.10) cannot lead to homosexuality.

Research Question Three: *What are the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on class-level?*

Table 4.3: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviations on the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on class-level

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std	Remark
21	Junior class students can exhibit homosexual behaviours	144	123	81	52	2.90	1.04	Agreed
22	Senior class students are liable to exhibit sexual related behaviours	119	152	87	42	2.87	0.96	Agreed
23	Adolescent at senior class is a stage for all manner of homosexual behaviours	111	187	85	26	2.94	0.86	Agreed
24	Avoiding unwanted pregnancy can lead to homosexual practice.	128	149	89	34	2.93	0.94	Agreed
25	Junior class students has no idea about homosexual behaviours.	30	69	167	134	1.99	0.90	Disagreed
26	Junior class students has idea about homosexual behaviours	142	173	59	26	3.08	0.87	Agreed
27	Senior students' peers influence homosexual behaviours.	143	170	50	37	3.05	0.92	Agreed
28	Junior students peers influence homosexual behaviours	139	161	72	28	3.03	0.90	Agreed
29	Homosexual behaviours are matter of class level	30	96	163	111	2.11	0.90	Disagreed
30	Junior or senior class does not matter in terms of homosexual behaviours.	134	134	91	41	2.90	0.98	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.78	0.93	Agreed

Table 4.3 showed the attitude of students towards homosexual practices based on class- level. The table showed that junior and senior class students can exhibit homosexual behaviours ((Mean=2.90, SD=1.04) and (Mean=2.87, SD=0.96)), adolescence at senior class is a stage for all manner of homosexual behaviours (Mean=2.94, SD=0.86), avoiding unwanted pregnancy can lead to homosexual practice (Mean=2.93, SD=0.94), junior class students has idea about homosexual behaviours (Mean=3.05, SD=0.92), senior and junior students' peers influence homosexual behaviours ((Mean=3.05, SD=0.92) and (Mean=3.03, SD=0.90)), Junior or senior class does not matter in terms of homosexual behaviours (Mean=2.90, SD=0.98), thus the students disagreed that homosexual behaviours are matter of class level (Mean=2.11, SD=0.90)

Research Question Four: *What are the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on religious denomination?*

Table 4.4: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviations on the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on religious denomination

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std	Remark
31	There is inter-religious debate on homosexual behaviours	35	33	154	178	1.81	0.92	Disagreed
32	Maintaining high level of spirituality can lead to homosexual behavior	62	30	181	127	2.07	1.01	Disagreed
33	Religion support homosexual practices	37	31	154	178	1.82	0.93	Disagreed
34	Religion sees homosexuality as a curse	143	159	56	42	3.01	0.96	Agreed
35	Religion and homosexuality do not match each other	155	149	64	32	3.07	0.93	Agreed
36	Religion has nothing to do with homosexuality	138	170	69	23	3.06	0.86	Agreed
37	Homosexuality should not be mentioned where there is religious belief	155	140	70	35	3.04	0.96	Agreed
38	Belonging to a religious denomination has nothing to do with homosexuality	42	48	225	85	2.12	0.86	Disagreed
39	Homosexuality could be an option to satisfying sexual urge.	53	63	123	161	2.02	1.05	Disagreed
40	Homosexuality is a devilish.	130	156	63	51	2.91	0.99	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.49	0.95	Disagreed

Table 4.4 showed the attitude of students towards homosexual practices based on religious denomination. The table showed that the respondents agreed that religion sees homosexuality as a curse (Mean=3.01, SD=0.96), religion and homosexuality do not match each other (Mean=3.07, SD=0.93), homosexuality should not be mentioned where there is religious belief (Mean=3.04, SD=0.96), and that homosexuality is a devilish (Mean=2.91, SD=0.99). However, they disagreed that there is inter-religious debate on homosexual behaviours (Mean=1.81, SD=0.92), maintaining high level of spirituality can lead to homosexual behaviour (Mean=2.07, SD=1.01), religion support homosexual practices (Mean=1.82, SD=0.93) and that homosexuality could be an option to satisfying sexual urge (Mean=2.02, SD=1.05).

Research Question Five: *What are the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on home status?*

Table 4.5: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviations on the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on home status

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std	Remark
41	Those living with both parents indulges in homosexuality practice.	225	85	48	42	3.23	1.03	Agreed
42	Those living with single parents indulge in homosexuality practice	125	176	67	32	2.99	0.90	Agreed
43	Those without any parents indulge in homosexuality practice	135	131	94	40	2.90	0.98	Agreed
44	Loneliness may lead to homosexual behaviour	140	152	55	53	2.95	1.01	Agreed
45	Those living with parents with an autocratic parenting style exhibits homosexual behaviour	162	144	59	35	3.08	0.95	Agreed
46	Those living with parents with a democratic parenting style exhibits homosexual practice	127	181	62	30	3.01	0.88	Agreed
47	Those living with parents with lassies-fare parenting style exhibits homosexual behaviour	163	127	65	45	3.02	1.01	Agreed
48	Those living with female single-parent indulge in homosexual practice	178	154	37	31	3.20	0.90	Agreed
49	Those living with male single-parents indulge in homosexual practice	78	165	88	69	2.63	0.99	Agreed
50	Home status has nothing to do with homosexuality.	98	120	87	95	2.55	1.10	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.96	0.97	Agreed

Table 4.5 showed the attitude of students towards homosexual practices based on home status. The table showed that those living with both parents (Mean=3.23, SD=1.03), those living with single parents (Mean=2.99, SD=0.90), those without any parents (Mean=2.90, SD=0.98) all indulge in homosexuality practice. Loneliness may lead to homosexual behaviour (Mean=2.95, SD=1.01), those living with parents with an autocratic parenting (Mean=3.08, SD=0.95), those living with parents with a democratic parenting style (Mean=3.01, SD=0.88), those living with parents with lassies-fare parenting style exhibits homosexual behaviour (Mean=3.02, SD=1.01), those living with female single-parent (Mean=3.20, SD=0.90), those living with male single-parents all indulge in homosexual practice (Mean=2.63, SD=0.99), meaning that home status has nothing to do with homosexuality (Mean=2.55, SD=1.10).

4.2 Testing of Hypotheses

HO1: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on gender.

Table 4.6: Summary of t-test on the mean rating of male and female secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std	df	t-test	Sig.	Remark
Male	187	2.56	0.92	398	0.448	0.583	Not Significant
Female	213	2.60	0.93				

Table 4.6 showed that the mean and standard deviation of the male students are 2.56 and 0.92 while the female students have a mean and standard deviation of 2.60 and 0.93. The t-test calculate value is 0.448, $p > 0.05$, this implies that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on gender. Hence, the null hypothesis one is retained at 0.05 level of significance at 398 degree of freedom.

HO2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on socio-economic status.

Table 4.7: Summary of t-test on the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on socio-economic status.

Socio-Economic Status	N	Mean	Std	df	t-test	Sig.	Remark
High	147	2.55	0.99	398	0.905	0.407	Not Significant
Low	253	2.46	0.95				

Table 4.7 showed that the mean and standard deviation of the high socio-economic status students are 2.55 and 0.99 while the low socio-economic status students have a mean and standard deviation of 2.46 and 0.95. The t-test calculate value is 0.905, $p > 0.05$, this implies that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on socio-economic status. Hence, the null hypothesis two is retained at 0.05 level of significance at 398 degree of freedom.

HO3: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on class-level.

Table 4.8: Summary of t-test on the mean rating of male and female secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on class-level.

Class-level	N	Mean	Std	df	t-test	Sig.	Remark
Junior	191	2.80	0.95	398	0.367	0.369	Not Significant
Senior	208	2.76	0.90				

Table 4.8 showed that the mean and standard deviation of the junior students are 2.80 and 0.95 while the senior students have a mean and standard deviation of 2.76 and 0.90. The t-test calculate value is 0.367, $p > 0.05$, this implies that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on class-level. Hence, the null hypothesis three is retained at 0.05 level of significance at 398 degree of freedom.

HO4: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on religious denomination.

Table 4.9: Summary of t-test on the mean rating of male and female secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on religious denomination.

Religious Denomination	N	Mean	Std	df	t-test	Sig.	Remark
Pentecostal	219	2.50	0.99	398	0.142	0.143	Not Significant
Non-Pentecostal	181	2.48	0.88				

Table 4.9 showed that the mean and standard deviation of the Pentecostal denomination faithful are 2.50 and 0.99 while the non-Pentecostal faithful have a mean and standard deviation of 2.48 and 0.88. The t-test calculate value is 1.142, $p > 0.05$, this implies that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on religious denomination. Hence, the null hypothesis four is retained at 0.05 level of significance at 398 degree of freedom.

HO5: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on home status.

Table 4.10: Summary of t-test on the mean rating of male and female secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on home status.

Gender	N	Mean	Std	df	t-test	Sig.	Remark
Broken	245	2.97	0.97	398	0.356	0.448	Not Significant
Non-broken	155	2.93	0.98				

Table 4.10 showed that the mean and standard deviation of the broken home students are 2.97 and 0.97 while the non-broken home students respondents have a mean and standard deviation of 2.93 and 0.98. The t-test calculate value is 0.356, $p > 0.05$, this implies that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on home status. Hence, the null hypothesis five is retained at 0.05 level of significance at 398 degree of freedom.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on gender. The result of this reviewed that the male and female students have similar negative attitude towards homosexuality. The finding of this study contradicts the findings of Kyes and Tumbelaka, 2004, Herek, 2008, Hansen, 2002 and Oliver and Hyde, (2005) whose findings revealed that heterosexual men tend to manifest higher levels of prejudice against homosexuals than do heterosexual women. The finding of this study affirms the finding of Lim (2002) who carried out a descriptive survey study on gender differences and attitudes towards homosexuality and find that both male and female have negative attitudes towards homosexuals.

The study examined the attitude towards homosexuality practices based on socio-economic status of parents. The result showed that homosexuality is not socio-economically biased because the students agreed that children from high and low socio-economic home indulge in homosexuality as a result of too much internet gadgets at students' disposal, lack of freedom, lack of money and acting on fellow rich friends' instruction. Again, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on socio-economic status. The finding of the result of this study agrees with the assertion of Dugmore and Cocker (2008), Hicks (2008), Camilleri and Ryan's (2006) that homosexuality is not a socioeconomic based problem hence both children of high and low socioeconomic status are seen practicing homosexuality. But disagrees with Next, Hall (2010) who found that gay, lesbian and bisexual adoptions are significantly influenced by socioeconomic status,

participants that were sampled were from both high and low socioeconomic status with those from high socioeconomic status showing positive tolerance toward homosexuality.

The study examined the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on class-level. The result showed that homosexuality is not dependent on a particular class level as students of junior and senior classes can exhibit homosexual behaviours, with adolescence stage, avoiding unwanted pregnancy, peers influence etc. being major contributors of homosexual behaviours. In addition, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on class-level. The finding of this study affirmed the assertion of Odeigah, Rasaki, Ajibola, Hafsat, Sule, and Musah (2019) and Winnie, Elizebeth and McC, (2016) that majority of the students 305 (69.5%) were between 16 – 20 years.

The study examined the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on religious denomination. The result showed that religious denomination is not a factor that determines the attitude of students towards homosexuality as the students from Pentecostal and non-Pentecostal background viewed homosexuality as a curse, religion and homosexuality as having nothing in common, and homosexuality as something not to be mentioned where there is religious belief because homosexuality is a devilish. Furthermore, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on religious denomination. The finding of this study affirmed the findings of Olson et al., 2006; Stulhofer and Rimac, 2009; Whitley, 2009, Maher, 2013; Schwartz, 2012 and Whitley, (2009) that there is a substantial association between religiousness and negative attitudes towards homosexuality. The finding also agreed with the finding of Finlay and Walther (2003) that members of Conservative Protestant denominations held the most negative attitudes towards homosexuals, followed by moderate Protestants and Catholics (Maher, 2013; Schwartz, 2012; Whitley, 2009).

The study examined the attitude of the students towards homosexuality practices based on home status. The result showed that the attitude of students towards homosexuality is not subjected to a particular home status being that the students agreed that children living with both parents, single parents, without any parents can all indulge in homosexuality practice. Again, homosexuality is not bound to only autocratic parenting style, democratic parenting style, lassies-fare parenting style, female single-parenting, male single-parents, which clearly implies that students from all the mentioned background can still indulge in homosexuality. It is also clear that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school students on their attitude towards homosexuality practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government based on home status. The result of this study agreed with the finding of Agbedanu (2012) reported that whatever behaviour put up by members of the family is what the student copies. The finding of this study disagreed with the finding of Kasoma (2012) who maintained that the home environment is a strong predictor of the future behaviour of students and an impact of broken homes touches almost every aspect of life.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the attitude of students towards homosexual practices in Obio-Akpor Local Government area. The result showed that the attitude of students towards homosexual practices is not subjected to gender, socio-economic status, class level, religious denomination, and home status. Again, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of the students' responses on their attitude towards homosexual practices based on gender, socio-economic status, class level, religious denomination and home status.

RECOMMENDATION

1. The male and female students should be encouraged to retain the same attitude towards homosexuality, also more campaigns should be organized to enlighten the students about the consequences of homosexuality.
2. Since the socio-economic status of the students' parents is not a factor that determine their attitude towards the homosexual behaviours, the students should be monitored and provided with the necessary basic needs and as well not given more than what they need in order to disengage their mind from taking homosexuality as an option for bridging their socio-economical gap.

3. Students in the junior and senior secondary classes should not be ignored at the expense of the other, as homosexuality know no class level.
4. The various religious denomination should keep up with their good work towards indoctrination against homosexuality.
5. The students from the various home status whether broken or non-broken should be monitored well and placed under strong guidance and counselling services from time to time more especially in the schools.

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